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Article in *SSRN Electronic Journal* · June 2016

DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.4133568

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An Exploratory Approach to Import Substitution Industrialization (ISI) in Turkey¹

Deena Saleh²

Abstract

The current article focuses on Import Substitution Industrialization (ISI) in Turkey. It adopts a retrospective approach focusing on economic, political, historical, and social contexts that shaped emergence of ISI, its performance, success, and failure. Understanding initial conditions in the country and its past development policy are prerequisites for apprehending its future development policies. The Turkish Republic was established in 1923, and faced political instability, economic hardships, and social changes that affected its development path. The article covers provides an overview on the ISI strategy that Turkey had followed ISI since 1929, until the government announced the departure to an outer-oriented economy in 1970s. Easy and complex stages of ISI are discussed within the Turkish context.

Keywords: Turkey, Economic Policy, Import Substitution Industrialization, Export Led Growth.

1 Introduction

Between 1838 and 1841, free trade treaties with Europe did not allow Ottomans to protect their producers and led to capital penetration. The Empire was a net importer of grains, cotton textiles³, and intermediate goods. Anatolian provinces exported agricultural products and raw materials. European manufactured goods and textiles prevented any attempts for industrialization (Pamuk, 1981:26; Hansen, 1991: 301-305). There was no modern industrial sector. Industrial production was based on flourmills, cloth, raw silk, and cotton yarn. These activities represented 78 percent of industrial activities (Boratav, 1981:165).

The Ottoman Empire was the last Islamic caliphate that managed to rule from North Africa to Eastern Europe. After the Empire collapsed, the new Republic⁴ of Turkey was found by Mustafa Kemal Ataturk in 1923. Ataturk adopted a modernization project (Kemalism⁵) to fully transform

¹This chapter is a separate chapter extracted from MA Dissertation that was submitted in 2016, from Hachette University, The Department of Economics, under supervision of Assoc. Prof. Muammar Kaymak.

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³ In the 19th century, cotton was main component for commercial agriculture in many western Anatolia districts. Balta Leman (Anglo-Ottoman) commercial treaty in 1838 harmed yarn productions. Raw cotton production flourished because of USA civil war of 1861-1865 (Teoman and Kaymak; 2008: 322).

⁴ The Republic was based on war-destroyed economy: World War I, Balkan War, War of Liberation (Buğra, 2007:39; Zurcher, 2004:166-176).

⁵ Kemalism focused on political and cultural reforms to build a modernized Western country. Ataturk adopted Western legal codes, secularized education, and adopted Latin alphabet (Bayar, 1996:774).

the state and the society through internal policies and reforms, along pillars of nationalism and secularism⁶ (Achilov, 2018; 6; Okyar, 1965: 99-100; Mehmet, 1983:50).

Given that in 1923, Turkey became a nation-state after the Republic was established by Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, this study focuses on Import Substitution Industrialization as an industrial policy that Turkey adopted during its transition after the Republic was established. It provides a detailed discussion of the context in which ISI was adopted; the political, social, and economic environment that affected the degree to which Turkey had succeeded in adopting the ISI.

2 Literature Review

Free Market Economy under the New Republic (1923-1929)

Although the Turkish government supported private sector in 1920s, resources needed to promote industrialization were not owned by private single entity. Private industries did not have financial strength. The modern industry was only transferred through wholesale import of technology and plants (Pamuk, 1981:26; Naş, 2008:9). Technology was either imported, or remained from Ottoman era (Singer, 1977:3). The economy stagnated between 1927 and 1929, GDP declined in absolute terms and no major structural changes took place in industry share. There was shortage of private capital and entrepreneurial talent (Hale, 1980:103). Post the Great Depression, the liberal economic policy was no more adequate, due to highly poor infrastructure and lack of private capital (Maxfield and Nolt, 1990:68). The world's demand for foodstuff and raw materials declined, and terms of trade favored manufactured goods. Foreign trade suffered due to falling prices of agricultural exports such as tobacco, and cereals. Living standards deteriorated, tax burdens increased, and society was dissatisfied (Okyar, 1979:327; Owen and Pamuk, 1998:13-17; Naş, 2008:9; Pamuk, 1981:26).

The failure of laissez-faire was owing to inability of private sector to carry on needed level of investment, and large-scale industrialization in Soviet Union, so the Turkish government assumed direct responsibility in planning and producing (Okyar, 1965: 99; Bayar, 1996:775). Moreover, Turkey had its central bank in 1930, but did not have a monetary policy (Hansen, 1991: 316-449; Naş, 2008:9; Okyar, 1965: 99; Boratav, 1981: 171). Owing to these factors, the Turkish state already initiated steps towards protectionism before 1929, through controls on foreign exchange and foreign trade (Pamuk, 2010:23; Zurcher, 2004: 178).

Initiation of ISI and Role of State Economic Enterprises (1930-1950)

During 1930s, the aim was internal regional development and urban planning was priority in development agenda (Pamuk, 2008:275; Keskinok, 2010:174; Pamuk, 2010:23). During 1930s Turkey's exports were in better position compared to other developing countries, but its terms of trade were harmed as well. The local industry improved in terms of profitability, but

⁶ Secularism was not in terms of Godless state, it meant state would not assume a religious role, to avoid social and political divisions. Supremacy of national willingness (Ulusal Egemenlik) meant the state's duty was improving people's lives, promoting reforms in social, economic, and legal spheres (Mehmet, 1983:51).

interventionism was better for industrialization, owing to absent trust in capitalist model (Hale, 1980:103).

Industrialization was based on private entrepreneurship, and government intervention when needed. ISI was done in areas like sugar, textiles, and cement, domestically available. The government could increase prices in monopolies and abolish any quantitative restrictions on foreign trade (Hansen, 1991: 313). Protectionism allowed the country to accumulate capital needed for industrialization. Partnership between public and private sector created high productive projects. Government protected the economy in face of external capitalism, through its non-capitalist strategy, inspired by Soviets (Naş, 2008: 24-25). Moving to agriculture, which was the most important sector, its recovery to pre-WWI levels took place at the beginning of 1930s (Zurcher, 2004:166). Agricultural development was to improve life standards of rural population and increase supply of raw materials. The government increased commercialization and exportation in agriculture, and subsidized input markets to increase usage of tractors. Transport network was improved through highways to create integrated local markets (Hansen, 1991: 314-316).

Between 1923 and 1943, the Turkish public sector handled major industries such as paper, sugar, and iron (Sayek and Selover, 2002:209). Due to increased number of State Economic Enterprises (SEEs), a legal framework was needed to standardize their practices. In Law No. 3460, SEEs were defined as enterprises with state-owned capital. Each enterprise could set up subsidiary organizations and compete with private firms, allowing for establishing mixed companies. Enterprises behaved as business and were responsible for their capital through administrative and financial autonomy. Profit was the main motive for each enterprise. On legal side, they had separate legal entities. Moreover, every enterprise followed a certain ministry. SEEs were superimposed in many sectors (Okyar, 1965:102-105).

A development process could be initiated through SEEs, but it can lead to a mixed economy model. If resource allocation would be based on supply and demand, and private sector would operate as well. Efficiency and equity were complementary goals. Efficient economic management in economic sectors would create equality, and efficiency would ensure that customers' needs were met by supplied goods in the market. The state should focus on minimizing social and economic inequalities rather than involving directly in the production (Mehmet, 1983:55). Goods of SEEs had low prices, which did not cover total costs. Reduction in real wages aimed to reduce expenditures in Gross National Income (Arıcanlı and Rodrik, 1990:1345). SEEs signaled management rigidity, bureaucracy, high losses, and inefficiencies due to increasing government intervention, banks did not have financial or monetary autonomy (Kamrava, 2012:97). SEEs incurred financial losses and obtained credits from Central Bank. SEEs were intended to be autonomous and free of bureaucracy. However, ministries' interference with administrative decisions adversely affected creativity and flexibility. Under etatism, government could set up price controls through legislation and constrain profit margins (Zurcher, 2004: 198).

Some contradictions emerged from dependency on SEEs. First, industrialization based on SEEs promoted monopoly and prevented market competition. High-cost local industry was developed through credibility to protectionism. However, SEEs did not abide by the main goal, which was to "take-off" then hand it over to private sector. They were rather institutionalized and serving elite. Therefore, inefficiency and mismanagement and high subsidies were severe causes of failure (Owen and Pamuk, 1998:28; Mehmet, 1983:47).

After WWII, the Turkish economy recovered. It was better than Middle East, Africa, and South Asia, but worse than Southern Europe and Latin America (Pamuk, 2010:18). World War II led to surge in global prices, but Germany and its Allies increased demand for Turkish exports. Turkish imports were constrained to emphasize protection (Singer, 1977:14-15). Domestic demand was high for economic reforms, flexible management, autonomous state enterprises, and a distinct private sector (Kili, 1980:390).

Five-Year Industrial Plans

Five-year plans and public investments were instruments of development policy to reach take-off stage. There was an interest-free loan⁷ up to \$ 18 million, and repayment was in form of unspecified product quantities. (Mehmet, 1983:52). The first five-year plan was drawn in 1933 with technical and financial support of Soviets, and was approved in 1934 (Richards and Waterbury, 1990:25-26). In 1932, the Soviet delegation wrote report on Turkish industrial development, and the \$8 million gold aid to industrialization program (Zurcher, 2004:197). The report by Soviet⁸ Professor Orlov shaped the first industrial plan, but only superficialities of Soviet planning were adopted (Hale, 1980:104-105). The plan was set up after nationalization of foreign companies. Main needs of the country were development, protected markets, and industries internally developed. There was proposal for building 20 factories, efficient investment and foreign trade arrangements, integration of transportation system to meet industries' needs. Industry's locations were selected based on proximity to labor force, security, housing opportunities, and raw materials (Keskinok, 2010:179).

The plan aimed at producing consumer and producer goods using available domestic resources, increasing employment through better allocation of labor surplus, and building factories serving some sectors such as: paper, iron, steel, and chemicals. In 1933, Sümer Bank replaced State Industrialization Office and Industrial Credit Bank to supervise and execute the plan (Günçe, 1967: 13-17). The focus was on capital goods and heavy industry (Singer, 1977: 9). Moreover, strategic nature of six goods was declared, three whites: textiles, flour, and refined sugar, three blacks: coal, petroleum, and iron. They were sold by state monopolies. State revenues were obtained through customs and profits from agricultural monopoly. In 1933, the ten-years old Turkish Republic was first nation of "Third World" to define its planned economy (Finefrock, 1981:377; Waterbury, 1999:333).

The plan, however, did not reflect a well-planned industrialization model. Selection of industries was based on pure economic criteria such as domestic raw materials availability and essential imports' substitutes. Turkey had a historical comparative advantage in textiles, steel, iron, paper, and cement. Therefore, investments targeted consumer and investment goods industries. Moreover, noneconomic factors such as cultural, social, and strategic considerations affected the implemented policy. Iron and steel plants represented strategically important investments for railways and armaments industry. Two plants were in Istanbul, while majority of new fourteen plants were located in central and western Anatolia. This distribution of new plants aimed at spreading benefits of industrialization (Finefrock, 1981:382; Okyar, 1965:102). In 1937, total industrial output grew at 10.3 percent in 1937 and 15.7 in 1938. On the other hand, agricultural sector grew slowly, due

⁷In 1934, a loan agreement between Turkey and Soviet Union was signed to support industrialization (Finefrock, 1981:377).

⁸Inonu was impressed by factories built in Stalin's era. The Secretary General of CHP Recep Peker, in 1931 visited Italy and praised Fascist institutions in a report. Atatürk predicted that this course of action would take place after his death (Hale, 1980: 104-105).

to biased selective price controls in agriculture. Financing industrial projects was through taxation and forced savings (Mehmet, 1983:53; Naş, 2008:18-19).

Between 1938 and 1944, the second five-year plan planned for building 100 enterprises, deepening industrial base, developing backward areas such as Eastern Anatolia (Bayar, 1996:775), and extending ISI scope. However, World War II led to abandonment of the plan. The industrialization priority was set clear in first plan, which emphasized a start of state-led growth (Naş, 2008:19). The goal was to realize positive effects of industrial development over agriculture, through establishment of mining, electric stations, heating industry and chemical industry. These plans were not solely industrial, they were social, and national inclusive plans (Keskinok, 2010:179).

The main difference between First and Second plans lied in emphasized areas. Second plan focused on capital and producer goods along with public works, it focused on solving individual problems through analyzing Turkish economic policy. The plan was assessed by to-be aid granting countries and top governmental authorities. Major sectors included agriculture, power, communications, and cement (Günce, 1967:19-20).

Five-year plans had a leading role in industrialization and capital accumulation. Easy stage of ISI used unskilled labor, which produces nondurable consumer goods. Turkey expanded its agriculture production and exports through liberal trade between 1947 and 1953. The ISI and its inward tendency were achieved by SEEs and heavy interventionism. Therefore, the domestic aggregate demand grew steadily (Çeçen *et al*, 1994:39). However, both plans did not draw a comprehensive development plan, due to limited goals. There was no economic analysis covering national income growth. They included investment and output targets for listed industries. Banks had to operate as normal banks; they could open branches and accept public deposits. Majority of resources was from government loans and budget allocations, so they were more like state holding companies (Hale, 1980:101). Both plans addressed the question of what development should be, rather than estimating potential development (Keskinok, 2010:179).

Political and economic changes in Turkey were caused by internal and external factors after WWII: dissatisfaction with ruling party CHP (Cumhuriyet Halk Partisi), agricultural producers and small peasants that suffered taxes and provision of urban areas. Globally, the USA emergence as a new dominant power shifted economic policies towards free market⁹. Many developing countries cooperated with West, especially the Marshall Plan¹⁰ for economic and military goals during 1948 (Pamuk, 2008:281; Pamuk, 2010: 25-26). Turkey was forced into the global system imposed by the West. It adopted liberal policies and admitted itself to democratic ideals while signing United Nations (UN) charter (Zurcher, 2004: 208- 209; Hiç, 2009:12).

Agriculture increased in the first half of 1950s due to equipment used by some large farmers, more hectares cultivated, short-term credits, relief from tax payments, price support programs, and road network extension. Between 1950 and 1960, 2,000,000 hectares were distributed to peasants with no land. Land holdings were fragmented and of small size, rural population was rising, and labor, new machinery was wasted due to scattered plots (Singer, 1977: 218-228). The Turkish

⁹ In March 1947, Truman Doctrine was announced, and that US would support free nations and anti-communist regimes (Zurcher, 1992: 208- 209).

¹⁰ The Marshall Plan in June 1947 helped European countries rebuild their economies. The plan promised to support Europe, ensure export markets for American industry (Zurcher, 1992: 208- 209). Marshall Plan financed agricultural machinery importation, provided easy credit markets and foreign exchange (Pamuk, 2008:281-282; Naş, 2008:20).

government offered price supports to farmers. Although agriculture somehow improved, average efficiency decreased, and price-support system led to increased expenditures. Turkey became major wheat importer after it was a major exporter. By 1954, cereal output declined, agricultural production declined by 14 percent, and GNP declined by 3 percent (Singer, 1977:196; Maxfield and Nolt, 1990:60-62; Karasapan, 1986:31).

As discussed above, Turkey did not implement ISI fully, as government position was linked to merchants and farmers demands. Financial system was controlled to channel resources to agriculture, but potential industrialists wanted to compensate losses in restricted consumer goods through engaging in industrial sector. They invested in different sectors, such as consumer goods. World Bank in 1953 advised an economic policy shift from agriculture to durable and non-durable domestic goods. The report stated that low level of urbanization and under-developed industrial working class was in need for policy measures (Buğra, 2007:40; Milor, 1990:6-7).

Economic assistance fostered Anti-Americanism¹¹. It was believed that Democrats would keep power, help new middle class be powerful, and harm former bureaucratic intellectuals. The Cold War enhanced position of the army and its supremacy. Others believed that strategic importance of Turkey would diminish gradually because of development of new weapons, as Turkey hoped for continuous war. The exploitation of West-East conflicts for serving Turkey's economic interests would hurt its world position and eradicate its influence among newly rising nations. There was close attention from Soviets to social and economic developments in Turkey, hoping that public attitudes would be changed towards socialism (Karpas, 1964:71-72).

Import Substitution Industrialization during 1960s and 1970s

During 1962 and 1963, Turkey had basic conditions for sound economic development. However, impediments were lack of objectives and social causes (Karpas, 1964:50-51). The Turkish state had large role compared to other countries undertaking ISI. It dominated strategic sectors such as manufacturing industry and investment, with share of 40 percent and 50 percent during 1960s and 1970s (Boratav, 1986, 125). The State Planning Organization¹² (SPO) was founded to centralize economic interventions, manage central economic planning¹³, and allocate foreign exchange. SPO had to approve all investments to benefit from subsidized credits and tax exemptions, cooperate with Undersecretaries of Foreign Trade and Treasury (UTFT) in controlling and managing trade policy. Exchange rates devaluation aimed at accelerating exports, gradual management of liberalized trade. Tax holidays, credit provisions, custom exemptions, and investment incentives were provided by the state (Pamuk, 2008:283; Owen, 1992:86).

SPO was responsible for planning under the High Planning Council. Both long-term programs and medium-term five-year plans were drawn. The five-year plans were 1963/67, 1968/72, and 1973/77. A fourth industrial plan in 1977/79 was delayed because of foreign exchange crisis. The Parliament approved the First Plan in 1962. The plan was not only product-oriented, but it also

¹¹Anti-Americanism increased in 1960s due to Vietnam War and intervention in Middle East (Ahmad, 2008:246).

¹² SPO was a planning agency to create a market free of exploitive agrarian and merchant interests and support the market if failed to allocate capital in high-value added fields (Pamuk, 2008:283; Owen, 1992:86; Milor, 1990:2-3; Adly, 2013:30-31).

¹³ SPO used "planning by stages" technique. A macroeconomic stage was set, followed by a sectorial/regional stage, and then a project appraisal stage, in which concrete investment projects filled sectorial investment targets. Based on Keynesian model, macro stage was drawn. Sectorial stage used Leontief's input-output model. Finally, project appraisal phase used ad hoc evaluation method, which was committed to shadow prices, but had no real conception on how to realize them (Hansen, 1991: 360-361).

aimed at long-term goals such as balance in external payments, higher number of technical personnel, social equality in income and welfare (Karataş, 1977:4; Hansen, 1991: 352-361). The Third Industrial Plan in 1973 was based on heavy foreign debt, and lack of foreign reserves. Turkey did not realize balance of payment surplus through internal adjustments. ISI in energy and manufactures was negatively performing (Richards and Waterbury, 1990:322). In the fourth Five-Year Plan in (1979-1983), there was proposal to reorganize SEEs into sector-holding companies, change organizational structures and pricing decisions, Turkey had strong bureaucracy and state tradition, which influenced pace of public-sector reform (Öniş, 1991:164-165).

In 1975, unemployment rates were high because of slow growth in construction and manufacturing, decline of investments and exportable goods. The structure of imports did not change or decrease dependency on imported capital goods (Karataş, 1977:7-8). Between 1963 and 1978, SEEs subsidized private sector's inputs through price deregulation and capital accumulation. However, there were no autonomy and managerial incentives in SEEs, politicians and bureaucrats intervened, managerial elite was not encouraged to produce efficiently, monopolistic, and oligopolistic market structure existed. In 1977, about 44 percent of public sector investment was done by SEEs, but their contribution to GDP was 7 percent, same percentage since 1967 (Mehmet, 1983:56; Öniş, 1991: 164).

Easy stage of ISI was from 1963 until 1977. Domestic market provided some opportunities, but ISI did not move to stage of complex technology. Although there was income inequality, many population segments like civil servants and workers were incorporated in consumer durables market. Real wages doubled due to political and institutional changes. Labor worked in Europe; they had constitutional right, and their wages were easily increased by large industrial firms, which did not face pressures for export competition. The ignorance of exports of manufactures was a factor behind weak ISI. Export encouragement was expected to increase efficiency and competitiveness of industrial structure, provide foreign exchange, support ISI, and create backward linkages towards more complex industries (Pamuk, 2008:283-284).

In 1960s, 76 percent of employment was in agriculture, but low productivity and stagnation. ISI was biased against agriculture along with overvalued exchange rates. During 1960s the economic system was near *laissez faire*; between 1963-1967, GNI growth was 6.4 percent, 6.7 percent between 1968 -1972, 7.2 percent between 1973- 1977 during three consequent five plans. Turkey achieved higher than average 6 percent GNI growth rates for countries in same low middle-income category (Çeçen *et al*, 1994:38; İmrohoroğlu and Üngör, 2013:3).

Stages of ISI in the Turkish Context

ISI can initiate economic growth process if imports of nondurable consumer goods were replaced by local production, which is possible during an easy phase of ISI. Since consumer goods' production employs unskilled and semiskilled workers; it does not require up-to-date technology or complex capital (Balassa, 1971:181). The complex stage of ISI starts by substitution of intermediate imported goods such as petrochemicals and consumer durables (Salvatore, 1996:24).

A downside of ISI is squeezing the agricultural sector. ISI policies impose an "under the table" tax on agriculture, which reduce income due to overvalued exchange rates. Price controls, taxation, quotas, nominal, and effective rates of protection exist along with squeezed sector (Bruton, 1998:914; Cameron and North, 1998:53). Similar patterns of institutional changes and outcomes

follow up with implementing, such as external debt, balance of payment crisis, and inflation (Waterbury, 1999:326). Personal income can increase and raise the demand for manufactures. This means changes in output would take some forms: manufactured goods could substitute for domestic handicrafts, domestic production could substitute for goods once imported, or new products could appear. Changes in volume, and structure of output would occur (Ahmad, 1978:7). A successful ISI results in substituting both consumer and high-technology imports (Adewale, 2012:294).

In the Turkish context, between 1963 and 1970, ISI had positive performance, which turned negative between 1971 and 1977. Whereas one third of output growth rate was caused by technological change, the share of labor in agricultural sector declined from 77 percent in 1962 to 61.8 percent in 1977, and in manufacturing sector increased from 7.2 percent to 11 percent and from 15.1 percent to 25.6 percent. Persistent unemployment was caused by relatively slow growing manufacturing sector. Moreover, exchange rates and interest rate policies along with high tariffs and quotas diminished optimal capital intensiveness (Çeçen *et al*, 1994:40-41).

The dependent nature of ISI was evident when it moved towards intermediate goods industries, through importing technology and plants. Foreign exchange reserves decreased, and right government coalitions needed short-term loans, under unfavorable terms. ISI in Turkey generated profits due to large domestic market, high tariff protection, and state intervention (Pamuk, 1981:29). However, ISI did not generate enough foreign exchange, because of slow growing exports, increased imports of intermediate goods, high food consumption, gap between investments and savings, inequality between rural and urban areas, and high unemployment (Richards and Waterbury, 1990:248).

The unequal allocation of investment resources to sectors was a major problem. Most of investment targeted manufacturing, construction, transportation, and communication sectors. Technological changes due to new production technologies improved labor quality to some extent (Çeçen *et al*, 1994:41-42). The bureaucratic Turkish state provided subsidies to entrepreneurs: rent-seeking behavior in business was common; incentives for business makers were to access cheap credit and foreign exchange and import final and intermediate goods. Therefore, a form of distributional coalition emerged between state and business makers (Demir, 2005:669-670).

ISI helped in accumulation of industrial capacity, and it led later to success of free market policy: active exchange policy, austerity at home, and subsidization. Liberalization came later, so its effects were minor on exports. Export subsidies were main factor of success. Investments were negatively affected due to high interest rates and fragile financial sector, distortions in social and political context caused by price adjustments (Arıcanlı and Rodrik, 1990:1349).

The complex stage of ISI required highly trained labor and advanced technologies for efficient production. Absence of these factors negatively affected growth rates; oil crisis and high dependency on capital imports and intermediate goods were factors to consider. The government kept its expansionary policies despite first oil crisis in 1974 and deteriorating terms of trade (Çeçen *et al*, 1994:37). ISI failure crystalized after 1973; internal domestic political conditions, high inflation, Cyprus invasion, increased real wages (Hansen, 1991: 353-367), foreign debts, balance of payment deficits, decline in worker remittances, stagnant exports, exhausted foreign reserves (Çeçen *et al*, 1994:37).

Table 1 shows the structure of manufacturing sector in Turkey. It reflects a declining share of consumer nondurables from 66.7 percent in 1963 to 39.8 percent in 1980, and consumer durables increased from 4.4 percent to 10.1 percent. Intermediary goods increased from 20.5 percent in 1963

to 42.6 percent in 1980, while capital goods declined from 8.4 percent to 7.5 percent. It shows a declining share of employment in all sectors between 1963 and 1980. Employment share declined from 65.4 percent to 54.2 percent in consumer non-durables, 3.7 percent to 11.1 percent in consumer durables, 28.7 percent to 24.8 percent in intermediary goods, and 12.2 percent to 9.9 percent in capital goods. This reflects the fact that ISI between 1963 and 1980 increased output of intermediary goods and consumer durables, while consumer nondurables and capital goods declined. Moreover, employment declined due to capital-intensive ISI process (Boratav, 2003:133).

Table 1. *Structure of Manufacturing Sector in Turkey, 1963 and 1980*

Shares of value of Production %					
Years	Consumer Non-durables	Consumer Durables	Intermediary Goods	Capital Goods	Total
1963	66.7	4.4	20.5	8.4	100
1980	39.8	10.1	42.6	7.5	100
Share of Employment %					
1963	65,4	3,7	28,7	12,2	100
1980	54,2	11,1	24,8	9,9	100

Source: (Boratav, 2003:133).

Table 2 shows the structure of public industry for years 1963 and 1980. Share of public investments in consumer nondurables declined from 53.3 percent to 29.2 percent, capital goods from 9.8 percent to 6.2 percent, and consumer durables from 0.4 percent to 0.1 percent. Only intermediary goods share increased from 36.5 percent to 64.5 percent. Shares of employment in capital goods declined from 18.7 percent to 10.5 percent, in consumer nondurables from 57.0 percent to 53.9 percent. Employment share in consumer durables increased from 0.2 percent to 2.3 percent, and in intermediary goods from 24.1 percent to 33.3 percent. This shows increased role for SEEs in production of intermediary goods, and increased share of employment (Boratav, 2003: 133).

After 1975, increased political instability and terrorism were about creating a civil war. The experience of Turkish industry to compete internationally was mature (Pamuk, 2008:284-285; Mehmet, 1983:55). In late 1970s, Turkey faced a debt crisis when it suffered from increasing rates of imports and declining exports revenues. The state policies supported imports through over valued exchange rates, increased industrial imports, and terms of trade declined (Richards and Waterbury, 1990:247). Negative GNI growth, three-digit inflation, and high unemployment created social unrest and political instability, which ended by military coup in 1980 (Çeçen *et al*, 1994:44; Pamuk, 1981:27). Turkey kept expansionary policy and was detached from European economies. Budget deficits were financed by short-term debts from European banks under guarantee of exchange rate by government (Arıcanlı and Rodrik, 1990:1344; Mehmet, 1983:55).

High inflation and unemployment, labor unrest and political violence postponed Structural Adjustment Programs (SAP) by the Turkish government. Devaluation, import restrictions, and austerity programs reflected a need for a real reform (Baysan and Blitzer, 1990:9). Pressures by

International Monetary Fund (IMF) aimed to reduce inflation and unemployment. There was difficulty in importing necessary goods for industry, which operated under full capacity. The inflation reached 100 percent in 1980, oil shocks, real wages declined, income inequality increased, increased labor supply and less demand, unemployment grew at 5.4 percent annually between 1977-1980, stagflation occurred (Bayar, 1996:778).

Table 2. *Structure of Public Industry in Turkey, 1963 and 1980*

Shares of value of Production %					
Years	Consumer Non-durables	Consumer Durables	Intermediary Goods	Capital Goods	Total
1963	53.3	0.4	36.5	9.8	100
1980	29.2	0.1	64.5	6.2	100
Share of Employment %					
Years	Consumer Non-durables	Consumer Durables	Intermediary Goods	Capital Goods	Total
1963	57.0	0.2	24.1	18.7	100
1980	53.9	2.3	33.3	10.5	100

Source: (Boratav, 2003: 133).

The share of agriculture in total output declined to 23.3 percent in 1977 after it was 38.4 percent in 1962. On the other hand, manufacturing sector had an increased share from 22.3 percent in 1962 to 31.5 percent in 1977. However, absence of expected outcomes was owing to inability of expanding manufacturing sector to create employment opportunities (Çeçen *et al*, 1994:38). Protection rates were high: 68 percent in 1979, 80 percent of imports had quantitative restrictions, unemployment rate in 1979 was 1.5 million out of 16 million (Richards and Waterbury, 1990: 248).

Table 3. *Characteristics of Economic Crises in Turkey*

	1958/1959	1978/1979
Nature of the crisis	Balance of payments crisis originated from the current account, primarily caused by domestic imbalances.	Balance of payments crisis originated mainly from the current account, caused mainly by domestic imbalances.
Origins	Fiscal imbalances; steady appreciation of the real exchange rates; export stagnation and rising trade deficit	Fiscal imbalances; steady appreciation of the real exchange rates; export stagnation and rising trade deficit; distorted production and trade structure caused by ISI

External dimension	Peripheral; falling world demand for agricultural products in the latter half of the decade.	Successive oil shocks have contributed to the crises; oil shocks largely aggravated the problem created primarily by domestic imbalances.
International actors in the post-crisis context	IMF is the dominant actor in the post-crisis period: a typical short-term stabilization program.	Both IMF and World Bank are heavily involved; official assistance through the OECD is also important.
Political consequences	Collapse of the democratic regimes; Restoration of democracy occurs over a relatively short period.	Collapse of the democratic regime; longer military rule. Restoration of full or unrestricted party competition occurs over a longer period.

Source: Öniş (2003: 4-5).

Turkey witnessed some rounds of institutional changes. First, replacing the Caliphate with Republic in 1923 and modernization. Second, capitulations expiry and setting protectionist tariffs in 1929. Third round was in 1946, when multiparty system was introduced. Fourth round was in 1961 Constitution that rebuilt parliamentary democracy, started economic planning, and legalized labor unions. The fifth round was after 1978 crisis and dismantling of etatism, and adopting export promotion (Hansen, 1991: 421-424). It is clear how Ataturk had set the basis for preconditions to take-off stage (Rostow, 1959: 6). By death of Ataturk, the country has been following the dynamic path of self-dependent growth through “pre-conditioning” (Boratav, 1981:166; Singer, 1977: 5).

Table 3 provides an overview on crises that Turkish economic system faced and how they resulted in ideological and structural contradictions. Turkey stayed more than fifty years to reach sustained growth take-off depending on SEEs. It was the oldest developing country that achieved development through planning (Owen and Pamuk, 1998:28; Mehmet, 1983:47-56). State interventionism in Turkey was not successful. It focused on profits in private industry, and how to keep them higher than world market levels, there were no changes in efficiency or competitiveness. Uncompetitive market forces prevented new entrant (Milor, 1990:26-27). Sociopolitical concerns shaped economic expediency until 1980s (Buğra, 2007:35; Maxfield and Nolt, 1990:60-62; Karasapan, 1986:31; Mehmet, 1983:54-57).

In Turkey, institutional, political, and social environment contributed to economic change (Pamuk, 2008:273); pure economic and noneconomic motives shaped decreed economic policies (Okyar, 1979: 326). Turkey undertook economic restructuring to comply with economic institutions of capitalism, although institutional environment was reshaped, political and legal environment were not ready because of absent internal forces, no alignment was made between institutional structure and international organizations (Çetin, 2010:5).

3 Conclusion

As explained, Turkey witnessed some rounds of institutional changes. First, replacing the Caliphate with Republic in 1923 and modernization. Second, capitulations expiry and setting protectionist tariffs in 1929. Third round was in 1946, when multiparty system was introduced. Fourth round was in 1961 Constitution that rebuilt parliamentary democracy, started economic planning, and legalized labor unions. The fifth round was after 1978 crisis and dismantling of etatism, and adopting export promotion (Hansen, 1991: 421-424). Turkish economic system has some ideological and structural contradictions, which emerged during establishing industrial and economic base. Turkey stayed more than fifty years to reach sustained growth take-off depending on SEEs. It was the oldest developing country that achieved development through planning (Owen and Pamuk, 1998:28; Mehmet, 1983:47-56). State interventionism in Turkey was not successful. It focused on profits in private industry, and how to keep them higher than world market levels, there were no changes in efficiency or competitiveness. Uncompetitive market forces prevented new entrant (Milor, 1990:26-27). There was conflict between etatism emphasizing role of the state, and its inactive role in achieving social welfare. There was focus on economic and political priorities. Sociopolitical concerns shaped economic expediency until 1980s (Buğra, 2007:35).

Turkey's adoption of ISI was relatively success. The changing of political policies and interests of social groups led to shift into export promotion, which was again relative success. However, results were not up to expectations. In 1950s, the focus was on agriculture and mechanization, programs with IMF and World Bank, and rural population started to gain their rights. ISI was kept during 1960s, but the country entered crisis that ended by a shift in policy towards export-led growth and free market. Turkey was in need for right direction in economic development and political freedom: two conditions that could only bring a country out of any crisis.

4 References

- Achilov, D. (2020). Analyzing the nexus of creativity, Islam, and democracy: Evidence from Turkey. *Mediterranean Politics*, 25(1), 96–127.
- Adevale, A. R. (2012). Does Import Substitution Industrialization Strategy Hurt Growth? New Evidence from Brazil and South Africa. *African and Asian Studies*, 11(3), 288-314
- Adly, A. (2013). *State Reform and Development in the Middle East: Egypt and Turkey in the Post Liberalization Era* (pp. 1-256). New York: Routledge.
- Ahmad, J. (1978). *Import Substitution, Trade, and Development*. JAI Press, Greenwich, Conn. John Wiley & Sons, Chichester. Viii, 1- 128.
- Ahmad, F. (2008). Politics and Political Parties in Republican Turkey. In Kasaba, R. *The Cambridge History of Turkey*. (Vol. 2, pp. 226-265). Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Arıcanlı, T. & Rodrik, D. (1990). An Overview of Turkey's Experience with Economic Liberalization and Structural Adjustment. *World Development*, 18(10), 1343-1350.
- Balassa, B. (1971). Trade Policies in Developing Countries. *The American Economic Review*, 61(2), 178–187.

- Bayar, A.H. (1996). The Developmental State and Economic Policy in Turkey. *Third World Quarterly*, 17(4), 773-785.
- Baysan, T., & Blitzer, C. (1990). Turkey's Trade Liberalization in the 1980s and Prospects for its Sustainability. In Aricanli, T & Rodrik, D. *The Political Economy of Turkey. Debt, Adjustment, and Sustainability*. 9-36.
- Buğra, A. (2007). Poverty and Citizenship. An Overview of the Social-Policy Environment. In Republican Turkey. *International Journal of Middle East Studies MES*, 39(1), 33-52.
- Bruton, H.J. (1998). A Reconsideration of Import Substitution. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 36(2), 903-936.
- Boratav, K. (1981). Kemalist Economic Policies and Etatism. In Kazancigil and Ozbudun, eds, 165-190.
- Boratav, K (1986). Import Substitution and Income Distribution under a Populist Regime: The Case of Turkey. *Development Policy Review*, 4: 117–139.
- Boratav, K. (2003). *Türkiye İktisat Tarihi. 1908-2002* (7th Ed.). Ankara: İmge.
- Cameron, M. A., & North, L. L. (1998). Development Paths at a Crossroads. Peru in Light of the East Asian Experience. *Latin American Perspectives*, 25(5), 50–66.
- Çecen, A. A., Doğruel, A. S., & Doğruel, F. (1994). Economic Growth and Structural Change in Turkey 1960–88. *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 26(1), 37-56.
- Çetin, T. (2010). The Political Economy of Institutional Change in Turkey. In: Çetin, T., & Yılmaz, F. *Understanding The Process Of Economic Change In Turkey: An Institutional Approach: Economic Issues, Problems, and Perspectives* (Eds.). Nova Science Publishers, Hauppauge NY, USA, pp. 1-12.
- Çetin, T. (2010). *The Role of Institutions over Economic Change in Turkey*. In: Çetin, T., & Yılmaz, F. *Understanding the Process of Economic Change in Turkey: An Institutional Approach: Economic Issues, Problems, and Perspectives* (Eds.). Nova Science Publishers, Hauppauge NY, USA, pp. 33-35.
- Cizre- Sakallioğlu, Ü. (1992). Labor and State in Turkey: 1960–80. *Middle Eastern Studies*, 28 (4), 712-728.
- Demir, F. (2005). Militarization of the Market and Rent-Seeking Coalitions in Turkey. *Development and Change*. 36(4), 667–690.
- Finefrock, M.M. (1981). Laissez-Faire, the 1923 Izmir Economic Congress and Early Turkish Developmental Policy in Political Perspective. *Middle Eastern Studies*, 17(3), 375-392.
- Günçe, E. (1967). “Early Planning Experiences in Turkey.” In *Planning in Turkey: Selected Papers*. Edited by S. İlkin and E. İnanç (eds). METU Publications. Ankara, pp. 1-27
- Hale, W. (1980). Ideology and Economic Development in Turkey 1930–1945. *Bulletin (British Society for Middle Eastern Studies)*, 7(2), 100-117.
- Hansen, B. (1991). *The Political Economy of Poverty, Equity, and Growth in Egypt and Turkey*. A World Bank Comparative Study. New York: Oxford University Press. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/1991/12/440580/political-economy-poverty-equity-growth-Egypt-turkey>.

- Hiç, M. (2009). *Turkish Economy and Politics from 1923. The Foundation of the Republic until 2002*. Beykent University Press, Istanbul, pp. 1-229.
- İmrohoroğlu, A., İmrohoroğlu, S., & Üngör, M. (2013). Agricultural Productivity and Growth in Turkey. *Macroeconomic Dynamics*, 18(5), 998-1017.
- Kamrava, M. (2012). Structural Impediments to Economic Globalization in the Middle East. *Middle East Policy*, Xi (4), 96 -112.
- Karasapan, O. (1986). Turkey's Super-Rich. *MERIP Middle East Report*, (142), 30-34.
- Karataş, C. (1977). Contemporary Economic Problems in Turkey. *Bulletin (British Society for Middle Eastern Studies)*, 4 (1), 3-20.
- Karpat, K. H. (1964). Society, Economics, and Politics in Contemporary Turkey. *World Politics*, 17(1), 50-74.
- Keskinok, H. Ç. (2010). Urban Planning Experience of Turkey in the 1930s. *JFA METU Journal of Faculty of Architecture*, 27(2), 173-188.
- Kili, S. (1980). Kemalism in Contemporary Turkey. *International Political Science Review / Revue Internationale De Science Politique*, 1(3), 381-404.
- Maxfield, S., & Nolt, J. H. (1990). Protectionism and the Internationalization of Capital: US Sponsorship of Import Substitution Industrialization in the Philippines, Turkey, and Argentina”, *International Studies Quarterly*. 34 (1), 49-81.
- Mehmet, Ö. (1983). Turkey in Crisis. Some Contradictions. In the Kemalist Development Strategy. *International Journal of Middle East Studies Int. J. Middle East Stud.*, 15(1), 47-66.
- Milor, V. (1990). The Genesis of Planning in Turkey. *New Perspectives on Turkey*, 4, 1-30.
- Naş, T. (2008). *Tracing the Economic Transformation of Turkey from the 1920s to EU Accession* (pp. 1-199). Leiden: Martinus Nijhoff.
- Okyar, O. (1965). The Concept of Etatism. *The Economic Journal*, 75(297), 98-111.
- Okyar, O. (1979). Development Background of the Turkish Economy, 1923-1973. *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 10(3), 325-344.
- Öniş, Z. (1991). The Evolution of Privatization in Turkey. The Institutional Context of Public-Enterprise Reform. *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 23(2), 163-176.
- Öniş, Z. (2003). Domestic Politics versus Global Dynamics. Towards a Political Economy of the 2000 and 2001 Financial Crises in Turkey. In: Öniş, Z and Rubin, B. *The Turkish Economy in Crisis. Turkish Studies*, 4(2), 1-30.
- Owen, R. (1992). *State, Power and Politics in the Making of the Modern Middle East*. Taylor and Francis e-Library.
- Owen, R., Pamuk, S. (1998). *A History of Middle East Economies in the Twentieth Century*. London: I.B. Tauris and Co Ltd.
- Pamuk, Ş. (1981). Political Economy of Industrialization in Turkey. *MERIP Reports*, (93), 26-32.

- Pamuk, Ş. (2008). Economic Change in Twentieth-Century Turkey: Is the Glass more than half-full? In Kasaba, R (eds). *The Cambridge History of Turkey*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, Vol. 2, pp. 266-300.
- Pamuk, Ş. (2010). *Economic Growth and Institutional Change in Turkey before 1980*. In: Çetin, T., & Yilmaz, F. *Understanding the Process of Economic Change in Turkey: An Institutional Approach: Economic issues, Problems, and Perspectives* (Eds.). Nova Science Publishers, Hauppauge NY, USA, pp. 15-30.
- Richards, A., & Waterbury, J. (1990). *A Political Economy of the Middle East. States, Class, and Economic Development*. Westview Press, Inc.
- Salvatore, D. (1996). International Trade Policies, Industrialization, and Economic Development. *The International Trade Journal*, 10(1), 21-47.
- Sayek, S., & Selover, D.D. (2002). International Interdependence and Business Cycle. Transmission between Turkey and the European Union. *Southern Economic Journal*, 69(2), 206-236.
- Singer, M. (1977). *The Economic Advance of Turkey, 1938-1960. Economic Development in the Context of Short-term Public Policies*. Ankara: Turkish Economic Soc.
- Waterbury, J. (1999). The Long Gestation and Brief Triumph of Import-Substituting Industrialization. *World Development*, 27(2), 323-341.
- Zurcher, E. J. (2004). The Second Constitutional Period, 1912–18. In: *Turkey: A Modern History*. (3rd ed., p. 104 -144). I.B.Tauris and Co.